

HTLV

CONFERENCE

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P016

Coexistent Adult T-cell Leukemia/Lymphoma (ATL) and HTLV-1-associated myelopathy/tropical spastic paraparesis (HAM/TSP) in a Peruvian cohort of people with HTLV-1 infection: A case series

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Background

Adult T-cell Leukemia/Lymphoma (ATL) and HTLV-1-associated myelopathy/tropical spastic paraparesis (HAM/TSP) are the two main HTLV-1-associated diseases. However, due to their distinct pathophysiological mechanisms, they rarely present concomitantly. We aim to present a case series of patients with coexistent ATL and HAM/TSP within a cohort of Peruvian patients with HTLV-1 infection.

Method

We performed a secondary data analysis between July and November 2023 to explore the occurrence of concurrent ATL and HAM/TSP among patients registered between June 1992 and November 2023 at the HTLV-1 unit of the Instituto de Medicina Tropical Alexander von Humboldt (IMTAVH) in Lima, Peru. Data sources included case report forms (CRFs), pathology archives from our main referral hospital, and histopathology records from referring cancer centers. Data was stored in a REDCap database. Seropositivity was defined as one or more positive immunoassays. All seropositive patients with clinical diagnostic criteria for HAM/TSP and anatomopathological and/or flow cytometry confirmation of ATL were included. Quantitative and qualitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics.

Results

From an estimated total of 4670 seropositive patients, 10 patients with coexistent ATL and HAM/TSP were identified. Key features are shown in Table 1. The median age at HAM/TSP diagnosis was 46.5 years (IQR 36.5-63), with one early-onset case diagnosed at 18 years of age. One patient (Case 6) developed rapidly progressive HAM/TSP at 63 years of age, one year after ATL diagnosis. In the remaining cases, HAM/TSP manifested before ATL development. The median timeframe between HAM/TSP and ATL diagnosis was 4.5 years (IQR 2-10.5). The median age at ATL diagnosis was 50 years (IQR 45-62). Additionally, five patients had a history of infective dermatitis, and one patient had a history of *Strongyloides stercoralis* infection.

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Table 1. Patients with ATL and HAM/TSP.

Case	Sex	Age at ATL diagnosis (years)	ATL type
1	F	57	Lymphomatous
2	F	34	Unclassifiable
3	F	70	Smoldering
4	F	67	Lymphomatous
5	M	31	Smoldering
6	M	62	Lymphomatous
7	M	45	Lymphomatous
8	M	49	Smoldering
9	F	48	Acute
10	F	51	Acute

Conclusion

In our series, ATL typically developed after HAM/TSP, and this sequence tended to occur in the fourth or fifth decade of life. Therefore, it is important for clinicians to monitor patients with HAM/TSP for the development of ATL. Further research is needed to understand the pathophysiological mechanisms associated with this co-occurrence.

Keywords

["Epidemiology","Inflammation","Oncology, Other"]